

Table 3. Karna grain yield in wet rice farm trials in Karnataka, 1981-83.

Year	Yield (t/ha)	
	Karna	IR20
1981	5.6	4.8
1982	6.3	6.0
1983	6.5	6.0
Av	6.1	5.6

IET7209 (KMP39)] showed resistance to blast (Bl), brown spot, stem borer, and gall midge. It was highly resistant to Bl in trials at Ponnampet, Karnataka, the hotspot for Bl (Table 1).

In 1979-84 yield trials at Mandya, Karna yielded an average 4.8 t/ha

compared with 4.2 t for IR20 (Table 2). In 1981-83 field trials at 30 sites, Karna yielded an average 6.1 t/ha compared with 5.6 t for IR20 (Table 3). At Mudgere, where Bl is endemic, it yielded an average 4.9 t/ha compared with 4.3 t for IR20. ☞

Mutagen-caused molecular losses in rice and reversal by gibberellic acid (GA)

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Dehusked IR8 seeds were treated with a 1% aqueous solution of ethyl methane sulphonate (EMS), methyl methane

sulphonate (MMS), and ethylene glycol (EG) for 6 and 12 h to determine their effect on germination, cell wall permeability, α -amylase activity, and amino acid and RNA contents. Reversal of mutagen effects was studied by GA (100/ μ g/ml) treatment.

Among the different mutagens, MMS significantly inhibited germination, α -amylase activity, RNA and amino acid content in both treatments, and

substantially increased cell wall permeability. EG reduced germination and other molecular degradation less than MMS or EMS, but significantly reduced amino acid content.

Applying GA to seeds treated for 6 h reversed the mutagens' effects and improved germination percentage and other molecular contents (see table). Mutagen treatment for 12 h could not be reversed by GA treatment. ☞

Change of molecular contents during germination after different mutagen treatments.^a

Treatment	Germination (%)	Leakage of ions (mmho)	OD values		
			α -amylase activity	Amino acid	RNA
EMS 6 h	69**	0.026*	0.21	0.067**	0.41*
MMS 6 h	46**	0.035**	0.25	0.047**	0.37**
EG 6 h	96	0.013	0.17	0.086**	0.57
GA 6 h	100	0.014	0.04**	0.163	0.78
EMS 6 h + GA 6 h	88* (27.53)	0.014 (46.15)	0.18 (14.28)	0.143 (113.43)	0.69 (68.29)
MMS 6 h + GA 6 h	63** (36.95)	0.018 (48.57)	0.21 (16.00)	0.102 (117.02)	0.65 (75.67)
EG 6 h + GA 6 h	98 (2.08)	0.012 (7.69)	0.16 (5.88)	0.150 (74.41)	0.71 (24.56)
EMS 12 h	56**	0.034**	0.23	0.052**	0.40*
MMS 12 h	40**	0.043**	0.26	0.041**	0.32**
EG 12 h	95	0.022*	0.18	0.068**	0.55
GA 12 h	100	0.015	0.04**	0.162	0.82*
EMS 12 h + GA 6 h	59** (5.35)	0.026* (23.52)	0.22 (4.34)	0.057** (9.61)	0.44* (10.00)
MMS 12 h + GA 6 h	46** (15.00)	0.032** (25.58)	0.24 (7.69)	0.045** (9.75)	0.36** (12.50)
EG 12 h + GA 6 h	98 (3.15)	0.017 (22.72)	0.17 (5.55)	0.073** (7.35)	0.57 (3.63)
Control 0 h	99	0.010	0.15	0.168	0.62
6 h	99	0.011	0.15	0.168	0.62
12 h	99	0.012	0.15	0.167	0.63

^ap value: *0.05; **0.01. Figures in parentheses indicate percent reversal by GA treatment.

KMS5914-4-6 (Sona Mahsuri): a semitall, fine-grain, high yielding rice variety to replace Mahsuri in Karnataka

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Sona Mahsuri (KMS5914-4-6) is replacing popular variety Mahsuri in Karnataka. It was developed from

Sons/Mahsuri, received through the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project. Further selections were made for tight panicles and lodging resistance.

Sona Mahsuri is semitall and matures in 140-145 d. Plant type and panicle characters are similar to those of Mahsuri. It has compact tillering, fairly tight spikelets, and stiff straw.

Sona Mahsuri spikelets are brown and awnless. Kernels are medium-slender and 5.56 mm by 2.1 mm.

Table 1. Leaf Bl teaction of Sona Mahsuri at Ponnampet, 1982-84.

Year	Bl rating	
	Sona Mahsuri	Intan
1982	4.0	9.0
1983	2.0	5.7
1984	1.6	3.0
Av	2.5	5.9

Length-to-breadth ratio is 2.56; that of Mahsuri is 2.45. Grains are translucent

without abdominal chalkiness, and cook flaky with good volume expansion.

In blast (Bl) screening trials at Ponnampet, the Bl hotspot in Karnataka, Sona Mahsuri was moderately resistant, with an average rating of 2.5 compared with 5.9 for Intan (Table 1).

In 26 trials since 1980, Sona Mahsuri has yielded an average 5.8 t/ha. In 12 trials, it yielded 6.0 t/ha compared to 5.4 t for Jaya (Table 2). In 1981-83 field trials at 14 sites in Mandya and Mysore, Sona Mahsuri yielded an average 6.5 t/ha compared with 5.4 t/ha for Mahsuri. At 6 other sites, it yielded an average 7.5 t/ha compared with 6.9 t for Prakash (Table 3).

Sona Mahsuri is gaining popularity and may soon be released for cultivation. ☞

Table 2. Sona Mahsuri grain yield in yield trials at Mandya, 1980-84.

Year	Yield (t/ha)	
	Sona Mahsuri	Saya
1980	5.8	5.2
1982	6.1	6.0
1983	6.3	5.4
1984	5.8	5.0
Av	6.0	5.4

Table 3. Sona Mahsuri grain yield in farm trials at Mysore and Mandya.

Year	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Sona Mahsuri	Check
		<i>Mahsuri</i>
1981	6.5	3.5
1982	7.0	6.5
1983	6.4	6.2
Av	6.6	5.4
		<i>Prakash</i>
1982	7.6	7.3
1984	7.5	6.6
Av	7.5	6.9

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IR13540-56-3-2-1: a promising rice for irrigated land in Bihar

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IR13540-56-3-2-1 (R. Heenati/ IR30 (BPHS)// IR2823-399-5) was chosen in 1981 kharif from the International Rice Yield Nursery - Medium. It matures in 130-135 d, is semidwarf, has good grain quality, and is suitable for irrigated, transplanted culture. IR13540-56-3-2-1 is moderately resistant to bacterial blight and will be a good substitute for Jaya and Sita, which have become susceptible.

In state trials from 1982 to 1984, IR13540-56-3-2-1 yielded consistently and 27% higher than Jaya and 20% more than Sita (Table 1, 2). It has been proposed for 1985 minikit trials in farmers' fields. ☞

Table 2. Mean yield of IR13540-56-3-2-1 and check varieties, 1982-84, Bihar, India.

Variety	Site					Mean
	Patna	Pusa	Sabour	Dhangain	Tilaundha	
	<i>Yield (t/ha)</i>					
IR13540-56-3-2-1	5.6	3.4	3.6	5.5	2.7	4.2
Jaya	3.7	3.1	2.6	4.4	2.6	3.3
Sita	3.8	2.9	3.0	4.9	2.7	3.5
	<i>Increase (%over Jaya)</i>					
IR 13540-56-3-2-1	51	10	38	23	4	27
	<i>Increase (%) over Sita</i>					
IR13540-56-3-2-1	47	17	20	12	0	20

Response of selected minikit rice varieties to nitrogen and tungro virus (RTV) on the Cauvery Delta

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Medium-duration IET7301, IET7303, IET7573, and IET7230 were compared with IR20 and Co 43 at TNRRI in Sep-Jan 1984. N was applied at 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg/ha. There was widespread RTV incidence and varieties were scored for infection.

Soil was a clay loam with low available N, medium P and K, and pH

Table 1. Performance of IR1 3540-56-3-2-1 in state variety trials in Bihar, India.

Trial location	Grain yield (t/ha)			CD at 5%
	IR13540-56-3-2-1	Jaya	Sita	
	<i>1982 kharif</i>			
Patna	5.4	3.4	3.6	1.0
Pusa	4.0	3.4	3.3	—
Sabour	3.6	2.1	3.1	0.5
Dhangain	6.3	5.1	5.6	0.8
Tilaundha	2.7	2.2	2.3	0.7
Mean	4.4	3.2	3.6	—
	<i>1983 kharif</i>			
Patna	7.3	4.2	4.0	1.3
Pusa	2.7	3.1	2.5	0.8
Sabour	3.6	2.7	3.0	0.5
Dhangain	4.8	4.4	4.9	0.9
Tilaundha	2.7	2.9	3.1	0.4
Mean	4.2	3.5	3.5	—
	<i>1984 kharif</i>			
Patna	4.2	3.6	3.7	0.9
Sabour	3.6	2.9	2.9	0.4
Dhangain	5.5	3.8	4.1	1.0
Mean	4.4	3.4	3.6	—

Table 1. Grain yield and RTV infection of varieties, Aduthurai, India.

Variety	RTV infection (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IET7301	21-30	2.1 b
IET7303	6-10	3.8 a
IET7573	41-60	1.3 c
IET7230	41-60	0.6 c
Co 43	31-40	2.2 b
IR20	31-40	0.6 c

7.5. N was applied 50% basal and 25% at tillering and panicle initiation. P and K were applied basally at 50 kg/ha.

IET7303 had least RTV infection and yielded highest, followed by IET7301. IR20 had severe RTV infection and low